

ROAD KILL OF DOMESTIC ANIMALS ALONG THE NATIONAL HIGHWAY NO. 52 (BANDERDEWA TO BALIPARA), ASSAM (INDIA)

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ABSTRACT

Road kills of wildlife is well documented worldwide but the domestic animals are reported least. The road kills of domestic animals along the 157 km stretch National Highway No. 52 from Banderdewa to Balipara (Assam) has been reported in this work. A Global Positioning System (GPS) based survey was carried out on 26th March, 2019 and the road mortality of domestic animals have been recorded. The study found that dogs and cats are frequently killed by the speeding vehicles during the night time. The role of Prevention of Cruelty Animals Act, National Highway Authority of India and the residents along the National Highway has been discussed to avoid or minimize the number of road kills of domestic animals as well as wildlife and human beings.

Keywords: Road kills; Domestic animals; National Highway; GPS; Pets & stray animals

INTRODUCTION

The mortality of animal's collision with vehicle is well documented (Groot Bruinderink and Hazebrock, 1996). Roads play major role in killing animals by collision with vehicles (Frissell and Trombulak, 2000). Roads are known to restrict free movement of animals within the landscape and cause mortality due to accidents with moving vehicles (Forman and Alexander, 1998). Many studies have been done on road mortality of wild animals like mammals (Newmark, 1992; Drews 1995; Newmark, *et. al.* 1996; Richardson, Shore and Treweek, 1997) birds (Loos and Kerlinger, 1993; Reijnen, *et. al.* 1995), reptiles (Gokula, 1997; Das, Ahmed, Lahkar and Sharma, 2007) and amphibians (Vos and Chardon, 1998; Seshadri, Yadev, and Gururaja, 2009 Vijayakumar, Vasudevan and Ishwar, 2001). But, there are meager works on the road mortality of

domestic animals which raises a question whether domestic animals are of least concern.

The zones of human settlement (“the city”) are envisaged as the province of pets or “companion animals” (such as cats and dogs), zones of agricultural activity (“the countryside”) are envisaged as the province of livestock animals (such as sheep and cows), and zones of unoccupied lands beyond the margins of settlement and agriculture (“the wilderness”) are envisaged as the province of wild animals such as wolves and lions (Philo and Wilbert, 2000). Animals move across these spaces in a number of ways. Obviously, they make their own ways across these (and other) spaces creating “borderlands”—where “humans and animals share space, however uneasily” (Wolch, *et. al.* 1998). Expanding urbanization has led to more frequent encounters between people and large predators such

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as cougars (Gullo, Lassiter and Wolch, 1998). With regard to the relationship between automobilities and animobilities, we have two trajectories - humans-in-their-cars and animals-in-their-ecosystems - that interact to generate road kill (Michael, 2004). The Prevention of Cruelty Animals Act, 1960 Section 11(1) (a) Beating, Kicking, Over-riding, Over-driving, Over-loading, Torturing, Causing unnecessary pain or suffering to any animals and (j) Willfully permits any animal, of which he is the owner to go at large in any street while the animal is affected with a contagious or infectious disease, or without reasonable excuse permits any diseased or disabled animal, of which he is the owner, to die in any street are considered as non-cognizable offences. Pets are part of our everyday lives and part of our families. They provide us with companionship but also with emotional support, reduce our stress levels, sense of loneliness and help us to increase our social activities and add to a child's self-esteem and positive emotional development. In return, as responsible pet owners we need to ensure that our animals are kept healthy, fit, get nutritious food, love and affection and proper housing and care (Global Animal Medicines Association). Road kills of wildlife is well documented worldwide and given due importance but the domestic animals are least reported. The study is an attempt to explore the status of roadside mortality of domestic animals along the National Highway No. 52 between Banderdewa and Balipara (Assam).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study encompasses a 157 km stretch of National Highway No. 52. The stretch of road lies in between 26° 49' 01" to 27° 05' 38" N latitudes and 92° 46' 42" to 93° 49' 40" E longitudes. The major settlements along the highway are Baderdewa, Narayanpur, Gohpur, Biswanath Chariali and Balipara (Figure – 1). Besides, there are many small settlements in between the major settlements like Behali, Jamuguri, Soibari, Tupiya, etc. In other words, there is presence of either major or minor settlements throughout the national highway. A Global

Positioning System (GPS) based survey was carried out on 26th March, 2019 along the National Highway and the road mortality of domestic animals has been recorded. The survey was conducted in between 6.00 to 11.00 AM in the morning by moving car at 30 to 40 km/h speed. The location of dead animals (both latitude and longitude) as well as the possible cause of dead was ascertained on each point. Further, the nearby residents have been interacted to understand their perception on the road kills of domestic animals.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The survey recorded 22 road kills on a single day that consists of domestic animals like dog, cat, goat and calf. Most of the road kills were dogs i.e. 11 followed by cats 9 and 1 each of goat and calf (Table – 1). Dogs and cats are the most common pet animals as well as stray animals in the locality. Hence, the road kills of these animals by the speeding vehicles were found to be more. The other domesticated animals like goats and cows were found be killed less however, the cases may be high if the count is made for more number of days.

The interactions with the nearby residents revealed that most of the road kills are stray animals. Most of the road kills have been reported to occur during the night time. How these animals became stray or what and where is the source of origin remains unanswered. The willful permitting of any animal to go at large at streets by the owners is considered as non-cognizable offence according to the Prevention of Cruelty Animals Act, 1960 (j). The speeding vehicles, especially night super buses and goods carrier trucks and the defective construction of highway without following the norms of National Highways Authority of India appears to be major causes for such road kills. These vehicles exceed the speed limits set up as per the norms during night time causing casualties to domestic animals and even sometimes human beings also. There are specific rules for ensuring safety to the plants and animals along the highways. The National Highway 52 along Banderdewa to Balipara has been constructed bypassing the minimal requirements in construction

of highways. The height of the highway is very low with no scope for walking pedestrians and lack of proper fences. There are no bridges for pedestrians and animals for crossing the road. They are forced to cross the highway by waiting and avoiding the vehicles which results into road kills many a times.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The study estimates road kills of only a single day so the numbers may multiply if the survey is carried out for more days. Attempt has been made to generate awareness among all the agencies involved in the operation of National Highway, the concerned authorities associated with prevention of cruelty to domestic animals as well as the residents along the National Highway. A mutual understanding of all the agencies could prevent road kills of domestic animals, wildlife and human beings to a greater extent. There is a need of concerted efforts by bringing together the National Highway Authority of India, the Prevention of Cruelty to Animals Act, the owners of pets and drivers of vehicles and the public in general to minimize such road kills. These incidences are not only limited to domestic animals as there are possibilities of human fatalities also. Hence, the residents of National Highway must raise these issues with the concerned authorities to avoid the increasing incidences in the area. To increase the visibility, the roadside bushes should be removed regularly to avert accidents/collisions. Further, construction of speed breakers at crucial points can also minimize the road kills.

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Table – 1. Description on road kills of domestic animals

Sl. No.	Latitude & Longitude	Date and Time	Animal killed
1.	26° 44' 37" N; 93° 09' 52" E	26-03-2019; 09:55 AM	Dog_1
2.	26° 44' 35" N; 93° 09' 26" E	26-03-2019; 09:50 AM	Dog_2
3.	26° 51' 49" N; 93° 35' 12" E	26-03-2019; 09:05 AM	Dog_3
4.	26° 53' 58" N; 93° 40' 41" E	26-03-2019; 08:35 AM	Dog_4
5.	26° 53' 49" N; 93° 43' 59" E	26-03-2019; 08:25 AM	Dog_5
6.	26° 56' 35" N; 93° 50' 13" E	26-03-2019; 07:45 AM	Dog_6
7.	26° 58' 09" N; 93° 50' 40" E	26-03-2019; 07:25 AM	Dog_7
8.	27° 05' 49" N; 93° 49' 38" E	26-03-2019; 06:15 AM	Dog_8
9.	27° 04' 38" N; 93° 50' 31" E	26-03-2019; 06:25 AM	Dog_9
10.	26° 44' 09" N; 93° 00' 43" E	26-03-2019; 10:10 AM	Dog_10
11.	26° 49' 14" N; 92° 47' 32" E	26-03-2019; 10:55 AM	Dog_11
12.	26° 48' 48" N; 93° 15' 55" E	26-03-2019; 10:30 AM	Cat_1
13.	26° 43' 53" N; 92° 59' 09" E	26-03-2019; 10:20 AM	Cat_2
14.	26° 49' 22" N; 92° 47' 25" E	26-03-2019; 11:00 AM	Cat_3
15.	26° 44' 34" N; 93° 09' 23" E	26-03-2019; 06:30 AM	Cat_4
16.	27° 05' 29" N; 93° 50' 05" E	26-03-2019; 06:20 AM	Cat_5
17.	26° 58' 16" N; 93° 50' 38" E	26-03-2019; 07:30 AM	Cat_6
18.	26° 56' 26" N; 93° 49' 53" E	26-03-2019; 07:50 AM	Cat_7
19.	26° 54' 04" N; 93° 46' 59" E	26-03-2019; 08:10 AM	Cat_8
20.	26° 49' 42" N; 93° 30' 51" E	26-03-2019; 09:35 AM	Cat_9
21.	26° 48' 29" N; 92° 50' 19" E	26-03-2019; 10:40 AM	Calf_1
22.	27° 01' 42" N; 93° 50' 07" E	26-03-2019; 06:55 AM	Goat_1

Source: Field survey, 26th March, 2019.

Figure – 1. GPS points of Road kills of Domestic animals along National Highway No. 52 (Banderdewa to Balipara), Assam

Source: Digitized from GPS points using ILWIS 3.4 (GIS Software)

